

CAN FINTECH BE THE FUTURE OF FINANCE SCOPE AND REVOLUTION?

Ms. Prerna Pardasani

Abstract

This article explores the risks associated with online modes of transactions in the context of Fintech development. While Fintech offers numerous benefits, such as increased competition, efficiency, and improved financial inclusion, it also introduces new vulnerabilities, including the lack of safety nets, misuse of personal data, difficulties in customer identification, and electronic fraud. The study examines descriptively the impact of digital innovation on risk assessment and credit allocation, highlighting the higher riskiness of Fintech borrowers compared to traditional ones. Additionally, the article presents findings from a primary survey, indicating that while people trust online transactions for small activities, they still prefer physical banks for major transactions and lending/borrowing purposes. The discussion also touches upon the importance of regulatory measures and the potential for Fintech to complement traditional banking services rather than replace them.

Keywords: Fintech, Cryptocurrencies, Credit Markets

JEL Classifications: O330, O300, G000

1. Introduction

Fintech hypes abound. In the news, Fintech is “disruptive”, “revolutionary” and armed with “digital weapons”, that will “tear down” barriers and traditional financial institutions (World Economic Forum, 2017).

“By partnering with Fintech startups, banks will give their account holders the right measure of security and speed. Account holders can know that their money is safe, and they can enjoy the latest financial technology. This is the way to become a digital bank.”

The term ‘Fintech’ has appeared recently in business journals to describe the disruptive challenge to the financial sector of the introduction of faster, cheaper and human-centered financial services. The term has become a buzzword among private and institutional investors who invested more than 50 billion dollars into the sector between 2010 and 2015 (Accenture, 2015). The visionary statement made by Bill Gates in 1994 that “banking is necessary, banks are not” has become a self-reinforcing prophecy, with 6,000 – 7,000 Fintech companies across the world now trying to obtain a slice of the banking industry’s profitable business. Strategic advisory firms have already put the emerging Fintech trend at the top of their agendas, with the goal of providing universal banks with a better understanding of likely future scenarios. The growing interest in Fintech will soon be visible in the academic literature, but there is currently a large knowledge deficit in this field. Fintech is an evolving concept that has so far created little historical evidence or statistically significant time-series data for analysis,

leaving researchers only secondary data with which to work, or sponsored research carried out by large advisory companies. As signs are already emerging that such financial technologies have the ability to significantly impact the use of cash and current banking and financial practices, and may empower individuals living at the bottom of the pyramid, the validity of research into the

various areas of Fintech and the financial sector are apparent.

2. Review of Literature

To gain insight into the subject, we delve into existing literature. Some research has explored Fintech and its impact on financial services, utilizing both primary and secondary data sources. In this section, we will examine Fintech credit, its operational mechanisms, and market development.

2.1. Defining Fintech

Fintech is a rapidly evolving sector with varying definitions. It encompasses companies that leverage information technology to create financial products and services. Definitions differ on whether established financial institutions can also be considered Fintech, depending on their use of technology. Arner, Barberis, and Buckley propose a broad definition encompassing all financial companies regardless of size, business model, or product portfolio. Regardless of these distinctions, all agree that Fintech emphasizes intense information technology use (New et al., 2017).

2.2. What is Fintech?

Fintech encompasses technological advancements enabling new financial services and products. The Financial Stability Board defines it as “technologically enabled financial

innovation resulting in new business models, applications, processes, or products with a significant impact on financial markets and institutions." Fintech can affect transactions, fund management, and insurance, providing cost reductions, better products, and enhanced data utilization (lowering search costs, scaling data handling, secure data transmission, and verification cost reductions).

2.3. How does Fintech credit work?

Fintech credit operates through online platforms, employing various business models. In peer-to-peer (P2P) models, platforms facilitate direct matching between borrowers and lenders.

Once matched, the loan agreement occurs directly between them, shifting risks to investors. The platform serves as an agent for investors, handling record-keeping, collections, and repayments.

Platforms often enhance investor information with credit grading, setting interest rates accordingly. They encourage risk diversification and sometimes offer partial protection against defaults. Most Fintech platforms utilize an agent model for revenue generation, while some retain loans on their balance sheet, akin to non-bank credit intermediaries.

2.4. Fintech credit market development

Fintech credit has expanded rapidly worldwide, but its growth has been uneven across countries. China leads in absolute terms, while the United States and the United Kingdom follow. In terms of market share, Fintech credit represents a small fraction of total credit in most regions. It plays a more substantial role in specific market segments, such as unsecured personal loans in the United States.

3. Drivers of Fintech credit

Several factors influence Fintech credit growth. Research indicates that local economic development, a robust legal system, and reduced competition in the banking sector drive marketplace lending. Surprisingly, technological variables, like internet penetration, do not significantly impact Fintech credit growth.

These results have important implications for policymakers. They suggest that focusing on local economic development and legal protections may be more impactful than investing in advanced technological infrastructure. Furthermore, Fintech credit can promote competition in the traditional banking sector.

3.1. Demand factors

Local economic factors, such as income and unemployment rates, play a significant role in marketplace lending. Internet usage does not appear to significantly influence Fintech credit growth, and there is no strong evidence that consumer trust in the traditional banking system drives marketplace lending.

3.2. Supply factors

Supply factors include legal protections, technological advancement, and competition in the banking sector. The strength of legal protections positively affects Fintech credit growth. Surprisingly, technological factors do not significantly influence its development. Less competitive banking sectors tend to foster the growth of marketplace lending, while the impact of banking regulations is less clear.

These insights offer guidance for policymakers seeking to foster Fintech credit growth and enhance competition in the financial sector.

4. Methodology

A primary survey was conducted to understand the interplay between the benefits and risks associated with Fintech in the financial sector.

4.1. Research Question

This article explores the risks associated with online transactions, focusing on the benefits offered by Fintech before delving into the risks.

Fintech Benefits

Fintech introduces competition and efficiency into traditional finance. For instance, it has lowered the cost of remittance services and expedited transaction processing. This has global significance, especially for developing countries, where remittances play a pivotal role in the economy. Digital innovation in the financial sector narrows the gap between financial needs and available products for households and businesses, particularly in developing nations. Mobile money platforms enable unbanked consumers to make payments efficiently and provide data for tailored financial products. Marketplace lenders, often targeting low-income consumers and SMEs, facilitate access to credit.

New Data and Techniques for Risk Assessment

Digital innovation has revolutionized risk assessment. Traditional banks primarily relied on standardized data sources, but Fintech now leverages Big Data and Artificial Intelligence to gather more comprehensive and real-time credit profiles. This enhances monitoring frequency and allows for more informed lending decisions.

Fintech Credit: Access and Borrowers' Characteristics

Fintech lending is recognized for broadening credit access and serving segments with limited financing options. Studies aim to assess if this shift leads to changes in the borrower composition and the quality of loan portfolios.

The Riskiness and Regulation of Fintech Borrowers

Despite its advantages, Fintech introduces new risks, including business model vulnerabilities, personal data misuse, and electronic fraud. Regulators grapple with how to oversee this evolving financial landscape, addressing issues like lending discrimination, disclosure requirements, consumer protection, and cross-border operations. Striking the right balance between regulation and innovation is crucial, and some countries are implementing regulatory sandboxes to manage this transition. These sandboxes allow Fintech companies to test their services with minimal regulation while helping authorities understand and address potential risks.

Studies show that Fintech borrowers tend to be riskier than traditional borrowers, suggesting that Fintech lending might serve those who couldn't access traditional credit. However, it also underscores the importance of managing the risks associated with these borrowers. This research draws two focus areas for my primary survey:

1. Fintech expands credit access, particularly for marginal borrowers with unmet credit demand.
2. Fintech borrowers tend to be riskier compared to traditional borrowers.

This synopsis highlights the interplay between the benefits and risks associated with Fintech in the financial sector.

5. Results from the primary survey

In addition to the use of secondary data, we conducted a small survey in which the following questions were asked (a link to the questionnaire is given in the appendix). The responses to the questionnaire have been collected from different age groups and the results are drawn from the 100 responses collected from the primary survey. The question asked in the primary survey is as follows:

Do you think there are risks involved while using online modes of transactions?

According to the survey, 51% of people were not sure about the technicalities of online transactions whereas 34% of people think that yes there are risks involved while using online mode of transaction and 15% of people do not think that there are any risks involved while using online mode of transactions.

Fintech credit: access and Borrowers' characteristics

Fintech lending is often seen as an innovative avenue for expanding access to credit and facilitating market participation in segments with no (or scarce) financing opportunities.

The idea that Fintech lenders serve unmet customer demand is grounded in an emerging body of research that focuses specifically on credit markets in developing countries. Hau et al. (2019) show that online lending extends the frontier of credit availability to firms with low credit scores. Firms use Fintech credit to fund growth and

expand their product offering (Frost et al. 2019).

New online platforms are offering alternative models of credit intermediation. Usually referred to as marketplace or peer-to-peer (P2P) lenders, these platforms are providing increasing

amounts of credit to consumers and small and medium enterprises (SMEs). Whereas some firms participate in the lending activity using their capital base (such as Kabbage), most firms simply connect lenders and borrowers and do not bear the risk of default (such as Lending Club). However, the term "peer-to-peer" is misleading because most of the loans include funding from a wide range of investors (including financial institutions). These lending platforms have no retail branches and typically provide faster loan applications and smaller shorter-term loans than banks. They also replace traditional credit scoring models with machine learning and algorithms based on big data mining to assess credit risk, accelerate processes, and lower costs.

Another form of online credit is offered by e-commerce platforms such as Amazon, eBay, and Alibaba, which recently started to offer loans to SMEs selling goods on their platforms. The access to the transaction history of their users puts these platforms in a better position (relative to banks) to assess the risk of the loans. This type of alternative lending holds great growth potential.

The next question we asked people was about their preferences regarding lending and borrowing

According to the survey that was conducted there were 46% of people voted for financial technology for the purpose of lending and borrowing

whereas 54% of people still prefer physical branches of banks.

The next question stated was the preferred mode of transaction i.e. through banks or through mobiles. According to the survey that was conducted 78% of people chose mobile (online) mode whereas 22% of people selected banks for transactions.

There is a huge difference between doing transactions online from one bank to another to borrowing money or lending money and from the above two questions we can clearly state that even though people have started trusting online mode for small transactions they still prefer going to banks for major transactions and lending and borrowing purposes.

Payments and Transfers

Innovations in payments and transfers are changing the way consumers engage in financial transactions. The current system of value transfer is built on several intermediaries, such as automated clearinghouses and intermediary banks (corresponding banks), which sometimes make the process costly and slow. Innovations in this area make transactions between individuals (and sometimes across economies) easier, faster, and cheaper than in the past. In the area of payments, most of the recent

innovations aim to improve the user experience, leveraging mobile devices and connectivity, although the existing payment infrastructure remains the same (such as Android Pay, Apple Pay, Square, and Stripe). In the transfers area, innovative mobile money solutions such as M-Pesa make possible peer-to-peer transactions with mobile devices, without the need for a bank account. New business models such as Azimo and TransferWise allow customers to send money across borders by matching transactions with other users trying to send flows in the opposite direction, thereby avoiding the high fees associated with international transfers. However, the most potentially disruptive solutions in the payments

and transfers arena are those based on the new blockchain technology.

The next question we asked was about their major platforms for transactions. According to the survey that was conducted only 11% of people are there who don't use any online mode of

platform for transactions whereas 89% of people use some or the other way of online mode of transaction.

6. Conclusion

Many people remain hesitant to fully embrace FINTECH for banking, citing the need for accessibility in remote areas like rural India. Fast internet access can boost Fintech services but raises questions about banking sector

regulations. Although online transactions show promise, traditional banking remains preferred for significant financial activities. FINTECH enhances financial competition and offers efficient services but is unlikely to replace banks entirely. Instead, banks can adopt technological innovations to modernize their operations.

7. Reference

- Tang, H. (2019). Peer-to-peer lenders versus banks: Substitutes or complements? *The Review of Financial Studies*, 32 (5), 1900âA_S1938.
- De Roure, C., Pelizzon, L. And Thakor, A. V. (2018). P2P lenders versus banks: Cream skimming or bottom fishing? SSRN Working
- World Bank "Remittance Prices Worldwide"
- Ancri, C. (2016). Fintech Innovation: An Overview. October,1-27. The rise and rise of financial technology: The good, the bad, and the verdict.
- Cogent Business and Management, 7(1).
- Suryono, R. R., Budi, I., & Purwandari, B. (2020). Challenges and trends of financial technology (Fintech): A systematic literature review. *Information (Switzerland)*, 11(12), 1-20.
- Shilpa D, M. (2018). Customer Satisfaction on Adoption of Mobile Banking Services: A Study with Special Reference to State Bank of India (SBI). *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*, 20(1), 44-50.
- Sitea, D. M. (2019). the Fintech Revolution. *Banking for the New Generation. Revista Economica*, 71(5), 77-87.
- Cornelli, G., Davidson, V., Frost, J., Gambacorta, L., & Oishi, K. (2019). ADBI Working Paper Series SME Finance in Asia: Recent Innovations in Fintech Credit, Trade Finance, And Beyond Asian Development Bank Institute.
- Hau, H., Huang, Y., Shan, H. and Sheng, Z. (2018). Fintech credit, financial inclusion, and entrepreneurial growth. Working Paper.
- Cortina, J. J., & Schmukler, S. L. (2018). Research & Policy Briefs.
- Giorgio Barba Navaretti, G. C., & Pozzolo, A. F. (2017). Fintech and Banks: Friends or Foes? *European Economy, Banks, Regulation and the Real Sector - Fintechs and Banks: Friends or Foes?* 97-105.
- New, T. H. E., Of, E. R. A., & Services, F. (2017). FINTECH, THE NEW ERA. 22-32
- Australian Securities and Investments Commission (2017a): "Survey of marketplace lending providers"
- Claessens, S., Frost, J., Turner, G. and Zhu, F. (2018). Fintech credit markets around the world: size, drivers and policy issues. *BIS Quarterly Review*, (September).
- Jagtiani, J. And Lemieux, C. (2018a). Do Fintech lenders penetrate areas that are underserved by traditional banks? *Journal of Economics and Business*, (100), 43 - 54.
- Buchak, G., Matvos, G., Piskorski, T. and Seru, A. (2018). Fintech, regulatory arbitrage, and the rise of shadow banks. *Journal of Financial Economics*, (130), 453-483.
- Haddad, C. and Hornuf, L. (2018). The emergence of the global Fintech market: Economic and

technological determinants. *Small business economics*, pp. 1– 25.

- EY (2016). *The EY Fintech adoption index: Exploring a new financial services landscape*. January.
- RAU, R. (2018). *Law, trust, and the development of crowdfunding*. SSRN Working Paper, (2989056)
- CGFS and FSB (2017). *Fintech credit: Market structure, business models and financial stability implications*. May
- Porta, R. L., Florencio Lopez-De Silanes, A. S. and Vishny, R. W. (1998). *Law and finance*. *Journal of Political Economy*, (6), 1113–1155
- Frost, J., Gambacorta, L., Huang, Y., Shin, H. S. and Zbinden, P. (2019). *Big tech and the changing structure of financial intermediation*. BIS working paper, (779).
- Navaretti, G. B., Calzolari, G. and Pozzolo, A. F. (2017). *Fintech and banks: Friends or foes? European Economy: Banks, Regulation, and the Real Sector*, (December).
- Braggion, F., Manconi, A. and Zhu, H. (2018). *Can technology undermine macroprudential regulation? Evidence from peer-to-peer credit in China*. SSRN Working Paper, (2957411).

8. Appendix

Questionnaire of primary survey

Below, you will find a link to a blank questionnaire from my survey, which I believe will aid the reader in gaining a clearer understanding of my research. <https://bit.ly/3fh0Y9r>